

Deterministic Lookaheads and Lookbehinds in Regular Expressions

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ABSTRACT

We give the linear algorithm for lookahead and lookbehind assertions in regular expressions by implementing the intersection operator which was well studied before in our prior research.

PRINCIPLE

We simply close the circuit in our algorithm [1] when converting non-deterministic finite automata (NFA) to deterministic finite automata (DFA).

The same is true even for NFA constructions which give rise to the question of relation between regular language algebra and features like lookahead and lookbehind assertions.

CONCLUSION

The potential of the method above gives the main result of the past research for efficient implementation of lookaround assertions.

REFERENCES

1. Syzdykov, Mirzakhmet. "Deterministic automata for extended regular expressions." *Open Computer Science* 7.1 (2017): 24-28.